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Independent Learning-Independent Campus: From the Perspective of Justice and Utilitarian Theories

Suratman¹, Umi Salamah², Sulaisyah Amini³, Fitria Dewi Navisa⁴

¹ Faculty of Law Universitas Islam Malang, Mayjen Haryono St., No. 193 Malang
Email: suratmandr@unisma.ac.id

² SMK Negeri 3, Terusan Metro St., Sumberejo Santren, Batu City
Email: omisuratman93@gmail.com

³ Faculty of Law Universitas Islam Malang, Mayjen Haryono St., No. 193 Malang
Email: amini.sulaisyah@gmail.com

⁴ Faculty of Law Universitas Islam Malang, Mayjen Haryono St., No. 193 Malang
Email: navisa@unisma.ac.id

Abstract

The Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 3 of 2020 implies that learning experience should be able to build characters of graduates in both hard skills and soft skills as expected by learners, the needs of the users, and the development of science and technology. The government set a policy of Independent Learning-Independent Campus, or commonly known as *Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka*, to set graduates ready to compete in the real career world. This concept was initiated by the government parallel to the theoretical perspective, giving students their rights to study outside their study programs in or outside the university; this is reckoned as a learning activity outside the university. From the perspective of utilitarian theory, this concept, set forth in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 3 of 2020, is intended to give countless benefits to university students as a whole to help them construct their hard and soft skills and to set them prepared to adjust to current development.

Keywords: Independent Learning Independent Campus, Justice Theory, Utilitarian Theory

1. Introduction

Higher education aims to grow the capacity and skill progressively and based on Internet of Thing (IoT) and outcome. These days, the era of digital technology has changed rapidly. Thus, the compatibility and flexibility to adapt to varied devices and platforms are vital issues in the infrastructure (Allah Nawazi and Muhammad Zubair Khan, 2012). With the presence of software and free web applications intended to improve learning, communication, and participation, social media users are increasing in number in universities. With these devices, academic content, discussion, and other forms of interaction are no longer restricted to safe and controlled academic circles, but they are accessible to the public (Julia E. Rodriguez, 2011).

Students' competence should be more prepared to get in line with the current development. Link and match take into account industrial and career scopes and ever-changing future. Universities are required to design and perform

innovative learning process to allow students to optimally and relevantly achieve learning outcomes including their attitude, knowledge, and skill. Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education and Presidential Regulation Number 8 of 2012 concerning Indonesia's National Qualification Frameworks require universities to adapt to shifting time through curriculum development that refers to Indonesia's National Qualification Frameworks. University graduates should meet the learning outcomes pertinent to the stages in the qualification frameworks and the education levels achieved.

The Ministry of Education and Culture (henceforth referred to as Kemendikbudristek), under the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture (henceforth referred to as Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020), asserts that learning experience should be able to build graduates' characters in both hard skills and soft skills as expected by learners, the needs of graduate users, and the development of science and technology, all covered in *Merdeka Belajar-Kampus Merdeka* (Independent Learning-Independent Campus). The learning process in the purview of this policy focuses more on essential student-centered learning. Learning in Independent Campus presents challenge and opportunities to innovate, to develop creativity, capacity, personality, and the need of the students, and independence in discovering science by exploring reality and dynamic in real life. With proper implementation and design of the program, both hard and soft skills of the students are expected to be well-constructed.

The application of the rights to learn outside the study program either in or outside the university, including the learning activities taken outside the university involve internship program in industries, community service, teaching practice in an education institution, student exchange, research, entrepreneurship, independent projects/studies, and humanity-related programs, all of which are expected to give students field experience that fully construct the students' competence and get them prepared for work or provide new career opportunities. The implementation of Independent Learning-Independent Campus is also expected to give answers to the issues encountered by universities to help them produce graduates capable of adjusting to current development, the development of science and technology, the demanding businesses and industrial worlds, and the dynamic of society.

The policy of Independent Learning-Independent Campus opens access for students to selecting majors they wish to achieve relevant to their own interest. This policy is to encourage the learning process in universities to be more autonomous and flexible. Education is always on its way to produce graduates who serve as agents of change in both narrow and wide scopes. The transformation and innovation that follow may be able to give maximum contribution to the progress of the state with its qualified human resources. The government made this policy to help set the students more prepared in the competition that the real career life could offer.

According to previous studies, Independent Learning Independent Campus has not been effectively implemented due to the following factors: (1) difficulty in conversing subjects, (2) difficulty in getting engaged with program partners, (3) mounting programs and activities demanding execution, (4) unprepared system, (5) human resources-related problems, (6) lack of support from lecturers, and (7) network issues.(Puspitasari R, 2021)

This research seeks to investigate the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus from the perspectives of justice and utilitarian theories. This step is expected to contribute to the enforcement of the policy in the time to come. How is the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus implemented in universities from the perspectives of justice and benefits? The investigation of this research problem is intended to figure out how this policy is implemented from the perspectives of justice and utilitarian.

2. Research Methods

This research studied related regulations such as Permendikbud RI Number 3 of 2020 and other regulations based on doctrinal research and mainstream methods, or commonly known as a normative method. Deductive stage was also employed based on the findings of philosophical principles and bases of positive and *in concerto* law applicable to settle legal cases.(Soetandyo Wignjosoebroto, 1974) This research also referred to statutory and conceptual approaches, aiming to delve into laws and regulatory provisions (Marzuki, 2021) seen from the aspects

of law that serve as their bases, or the values existing in the standardization of regulations related to the concepts in the implementation of Independent Learning Independent Campus.

Required legal materials were taken from library research and documents, representing primary data such as regulations related to the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus and secondary data involving literary books, research journals, articles related to the issue.

All the materials were further analyzed based on descriptive-qualitative methods, statutory, and conceptual approaches before the materials were presented in a description.

3. Discussion

3.1. Implementation of the Policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus

Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning National Education Systems asserts that “Education aims to grow learners’ potential and guide them to becoming individuals who only fear God, have noble values, are rational, knowledgeable, skillful, creative, independent, democratic and responsible”.

Philosophically, the primary target of education, curriculum, and learning is to optimize human potentials. Excellent human resources development in Indonesia is paramount. The movement of mental revolution represents a good faith in the development and continuation of the existence of Indonesia. This certainly requires coaching, learning, and character building as the main process for university students. Curricula relevant to jobs and the freedom to innovate, to be independent and creative in both lecturers and students characterize Independent Campus, and this is expected to shape adequate multidisciplinary capacity within individuals.

Education reform initiated by the Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Makarim implies that education serves as the core of a curriculum or the other way around. That is, the running of both education and curricula lie in learning activities. To provide academic quality, learning serves as the key to learning success in a curriculum. Departing from this understanding, the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus demands reform for a more adaptive curriculum for the future. Both education and curricula require learning efforts positioning education and professionalism to facilitate students’ learning process. Independent learning Independent Campus is a learning reform implemented in pre-school to higher education. Reform and Independent Learning are pursuant to Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020 concerning National Standards of Higher Education.

In terms of the Independent Learning Independent Campus program, Siti Mustaghfiroh explained that the concept of independent learning holds the concepts and objectives similar to the concept of progressivism education philosophy introduced by John Dewey, both of which highlight independence and freedom, allowing education institutions to optimally explore students’ potential according to their interest. He also asserts that independent learning also serves as concrete solutions to the complex issues in education (Mustaghfiroh, 2020).

Independent Learning Independent Campus is a policy initiated by the Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology Nadiem Makarim, covering two essential concepts. First, the concept of independent learning refers to the freedom to think. Nadiem Makarim argues that the essence of freedom to think should be initiated by educators. Such a perspective should be seen as an effort to respect changes in learning in education institutions ranging from primary schools, high schools, to higher education. Second, independent campus represents the continuation of independent learning concept. Independent Campus is an effort to give more space to innovate (Susilawati, 2021).

Universities should give students their rights to voluntarily study for two semesters outside their university. Students are also enabled to take credits under a different study program for a semester. The rights to three semesters taken outside their study program are intended to prepare students with skill to social, cultural, and industrial changes and vast development of technology (Susilawati, 2021). The competence of students should be adjusted to time that keeps shifting, followed by link and match to be considered in industries, career world, and

the future. The Permendikbud asserts that study could be taken either within a study program or outside a study program (Article 15 Paragraph (1) Permendikbud RI Number 3 of 2020, n.d.) with the learning process consisting of: (Article 15 Paragraph (1) Permendikbud RI Number 3 of 2020, n.d.)

- a. study under another study program in the same university;
- b. study under the same study program in another university;
- c. study under another study program in another university; and
- d. study taken in a non-university institution

Learning activities refer to Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020. The studies carried in a study program or outside a study program, as set forth in Article 15 paragraph (1), involve:

a. Student Exchange

Student exchange involves credit transfer through long distant learning using online system. University students' access to education has been improving due to the advancement of technology while conventional face-to-face class interaction in universities will remain in existence. Online mode is only supplementary to conventional learning in universities. (Todd A. Finkle and Evan Masters, 2014) This program allows students to: (1) study across campus (domestically and overseas) and establish cross-cultural communities, (2) build friendship among students across regions, race, culture, and religion and encourage unity, (3) transfer knowledge to settle education disparity between local universities or between local university and university overseas. The analysis of the research conducted implies that student exchange program should be preceded with partnerships and collaborations across universities, each of which needs to identify and accommodate input on the needs of partnerships from study programs. The theme of the activities of the program and course recognition should be covered in collaboration agreement; however, this program faces issues where commencement is not consistent, causing delay in students' mark submission. Thus, the administrators of higher education need to participate in long-distance learning and take measures in other forms of technology. Available training and workshop in effective and sufficient long-distance learning are the requirements that institutions need to take into account to initiate long distant learning.

b. Internship/Job Training

Internship program takes 1-2 semesters involving experiential learning at a workplace. An internship is focused more on career-oriented skill training, and the service providers are those perceiving the main benefits of each program held in the internship. (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019) This six-month program is relevant to 20 credits representing hard skills and soft skills. The learning activities also require partnerships with companies, non-profit organizations, multilateral organizations, government institutions, and start-up businesses. Students gain hard skills including complex problem-solving and analytical skill. The soft skills involve professional ethics/work ethics, communication, and collaboration. Such learning activities within industrial scope allow students to get more prepared for the real career world, and universities benefit from the information on issues faced by industries (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019).

Weight of activities involves free form, structured form, and hybrid. Free form represents six-month activities equal to 20 credits without adjustment to courses. Structured form is adjusted to the curriculum taken by the students, requiring 20 credits. This requires adjustment to courses whose competence is relevant to the competence in internship.

The research analysis results indicate that universities welcome internship programs in industries and businesses with the recognition of adjustment to the weight of activities as mentioned above as a part of Independent Learning Independent Campus program with open arms. The policy of such a collaboration with industries is proven capable of giving solutions to quality gaps. Universities are adjusting the students' competence to what job market needs. Internship is preferred by most students since it gives them a wider chance to be hired professionally by the companies where they attend internship upon their graduation. That is, students do not need to spend any waiting time in the transition between graduation and work, and this will certainly affect performance indicator of a university.

However, there is concern among lecturers regarding the likelihood that students may miss their courses when they have to be engaged in the internship. Changing this mindset requires more massive introduction of Independent Learning Independent Campus policy. Guidebooks seem to come in handy to enable lecturers, students, guardian lecturers, field supervisory lecturers, and supervisory representatives from partner companies to understand the mechanism of internship ranging from selection, monitoring, evaluation, to marking. Mark recognition is important in study programs, faculty, university or higher education data center where software must be ready.

c. Research

This platform gives students a chance of becoming a researcher. Research could take place in research institutions or study centers. Research covers three objectives: (1) developing the quality of students, departing from their research experience expected to strengthen researchers within topical scope; (2) enabling students to gain competence in research under the direct tutelage of research institutions and study centers; and (3) improving research ecosystem and quality in laboratories for the sake of researcher regeneration. (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019) Students are supervised when they conduct research according to instruction given by research institutions. Logbook also needs to be made to make a final report.

Once in a while students need to be involved in research led by a lecturer. This is intended to encourage students to master the skill in research, especially when they have to deal with thesis or final project. However, COVID-19 has forced higher education institutions or universities to adapt to the ever-changing situations like never before. Research centers are facing a huge challenge in managing research operations. Social distance requirements are not easy to fulfill regarding research management requiring benchmark, the participation of human beings, and fieldwork, resulting in a significant loss in research. (Shazia Rasyid and Sunishtha Singh Yadav, 2020)

d. Humanity Projects

Indonesia has been through several disasters such as earthquakes, volcano eruptions, tsunamis, and hydrological disasters. With these catastrophes, students are expected to serve as “foot soldiers” in humanity projects and development, which aim to (1) prepare excellent students who uphold humanity values to perform their tasks in compliance with religion, moral values, and ethics; and (2) to train students to have deeper social sensitivity and to encourage them to discover and delve into existing problems and to contribute solutions according to their interest and capacity. (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019) Students are supervised by lecturers and partners in evaluation and marking the activities they are conducting. Partners are not restricted to those living in the same countries, but some probably reside abroad.

e. Entrepreneurship

This program is intended to encourage students to grow their interest in entrepreneurship. With this program, students are expected to (1) have interest in entrepreneurship and to start their businesses earlier and under supervision; and (2) settle unemployment issues including intellectual unemployment among bachelor graduates. (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019) Learning activities may involve activities in entrepreneurship not existing in the curriculum of study program. In the program, students are supervised by lecturers, requiring 20 credits per semester or 40 credits each year. The indicator of the learning outcome is a mark of A for those managing to create their own start-up.

f. Independent studies/projects

Independent projects are complementary to the topics not covered in course schedule but covered in a study program or faculty syllabus, where students could initiate their innovation (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019) for further contests at both national and international levels. This activity could substitute for a course calculated based on the contribution and role of the students communicating with lecturers as supervisors.

g. Participation in village development/thematic community service

This program allows students to learn from experience by living in a real community, where they are supposed to identify potential, handle problems, develop the potential of a village and brainstorm the solutions to the problems existing in society. Job training focus on increasing students' understanding of their theoretical knowledge through community service experiences and reflection on those experiences. With job training, the politics of the transformation of higher education and society could manifest (Dan W. Butin, 2006). Following this program, students are required to prepare their final report. This program aims to (1) give students opportunities to implement their knowledge, utilize technology, use their skill, and build a partnership with stakeholders in the area for six to twelve months; (2) help accelerate rural development along with the Ministry of Underdeveloped Villages (Maimoona Salam, Dayang Nurfatimah Awang Iskandar, Dayang Hanani Abang Ibrahim, 2019).

The implementation of Independent Learning Independent Campus is aimed to improve the competence of the graduates either in terms of their hard skills or soft skills to set them ready to face current development and to shape them into individuals with excellence and good personality as the leaders in the future.

3.2. Implementation of the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus from the perspectives of justice and utilitarian theories

a. Justice theory

In this program, universities must give students their rights to voluntarily take courses outside the university for two semesters or equal to 40 credits. Students are also allowed to take credits in another study program in the same university for one semester. The right to take three semesters outside the study program is intended to prepare students to face social, cultural, and industrial changes and vast development of technology.

“Right” does not only refer to protection and interest, but also will (Paton, 1971). The term right does not only refer to an individual interest to be protected, but also the will of an individual. The characteristics that are attached to right, according to law, involve the following (Fitzgerad, 1966):

1. The right is embedded in a person or a subject who possesses the right. He/she represents a person with a title belonging to an object as a target and a right.
2. The right is addressed to a person holding responsibilities. Rights and responsibilities are correlated.
3. The right embedded in an individual requires another party to act (to be commissioned) or not to act (omission). This may be reckoned the content of a right.
4. This omission involves an object and a right.
5. Each right, according to law, has a title that represents a particular event based on which the right is attached to its holder.

Salmond argues that there are three definitions of right: freedom, power, and immunity (Fitzgerad, 1966). If a right (in a narrow scope of definition) is embedded in a person to complement a responsibility the person bears, the freedom provided by law for a person is complementary to the absence of liability attached to the person concerned. This freedom consists of interest of a person to act based on interest, and the freedom to act should not be interrupted by law. That is, the freedom can be defined to an extent where a person could carry out activities not proscribed by law. Every individual has his/her rights to carry out activities as he/she wishes, but not for those violating the rights of others.

The above elaboration highlights a clear boundary between a right defined in a narrow scope and the freedom according to law. Rights are related to what a person does for another person, and these are also related to what a person performs for himself/herself.

Justice is marked by a good relationship between individuals, balancing between public interest and individual interest. Justice highlights equality, meaning that every individual in society will hold the same rights as others. The formulation of justice stands on justice principles such as living a dignified life, not violating others' rights, and letting others have what they deserve. These justice principles set the benchmark regarding what is right or appropriate for one's life, and these principles are binding for all, either the members of the public or those with power. Since law is binding for all people, justice must be understood within the purview of equality.

Aristotle, a philosopher of ethical theory, breaks equality into two: numeric and proportional equality, where the former results in the principle “Every person is equal before law”, while the latter highlights the principle “to give others their rights” (Atmasasmita, 2012).

Aristotle dealt with justice issues from the perspective of equality. This principle requires humans and states to obtain their rights based on equality principle. Law should ensure that right distribution is maintained and protected from any violations. In this context, Aristotle differentiates between distributive and corrective justices. Distributive justice highlights how the state or the members of the public distribute natural resources to people. Aristotle argued that both followed equality principle, where he stated “there must be equality regarding what every person receives; the ratio one receives should be equal to the number of the persons receiving it, or the distribution cannot be made equal. When the same persons do not receive the same portions, or when different persons receive the same portions, disputes and complaints may arise (Bodenheimer, 1974).

Roscoe Pound viewed justice in a concrete form given to the members of the public. He viewed that what is received should cover satisfaction that meets human needs as much as possible requiring only the smallest amount of sacrifice possible. Pound once stated “recognition and the fulfilment of human needs, demands, and expectation through social control are on the rise; the efficacy of guarantee of social interest also rises; efforts to abolish endless profligacy are getting more effective to stop people from having conflict over the utilization of natural resources. In short, social engineering is effectively improving (Pound, 1978).

On the other hand, John Rawls conceptualized justice as fairness, bringing the principle “independent and rational people willing to grow their interest should be granted equal positions for initiation since these serve as fundamental requirements that give them access to congregations they wish to take part in”.(Bodenheimer, 1974) Those varied views of justice above represent human nature and give reference of how humans should be treated. Some view this from the perspective of freedom as an absolute part of the humans’ life on earth. Freedom is valuable in every individual and, therefore, failing to respect freedom equals to treating humans inhumanly. Thus, freedom allows humans to properly grow (Rahardjo, 1991).

The above theoretical view, when connected to Independent Learning Independent Campus set forth in Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020, indicates that this policy represents the presentation of rewards to students allowing them to grow. In the implementation of this policy, Permendikbud enables students to study according to their rights that allow them to study outside their study program either in campus or outside campus. That is, this regulation is relevant to justice theory that gives students their rights. The rights to study outside a study program either in or outside the university and learning activities performed outside the university such as internship, job training, community service, teaching in an education institution, student exchange, research, entrepreneurship, independent studies/projects, and humanity programs are expected to teach students direct contextual experience that contributes to the competence of the students as a whole and shape them into individuals that are set ready for work or to provide them new jobs. Thus, higher education/universities must deal with the entire students (in terms of intellectual, emotional, and social aspects) to get the graduates prepared for their future success.

b. Utilitarian theory

Utilitarian theory was initiated by Jeremy Bentham who opined that regulations and laws should benefit human life. Whether happiness comes from justice or from legal certainty in society is not important. A good law brings the greatest happiness to the entire people.

In classical Benthamite utilitarianism, the goal of morality is to maximize pleasure and minimize pain. Pleasure and pain are taken to be the common denominators of all morally relevant experiences. For other utilitarian’s influenced by Bentham maximizing happiness (“the greatest happiness for the greatest number”) is the goal (Thomas Morawet, 1980).

Jeremy Bentham, a utilitarianist, viewed that humans principally act to gain as much happiness as possible and to reduce their burden. This happiness is defined as freedom of self-expression in defending human rights (Pound, 1978). Related to other elements of law, Bentham believed that legislative drafting should bring about law that represents justice for all individuals, so that the legislation made could bring the greatest happiness for the greatest number. Bentham's view indicates that the elements of law including legal certainty, benefits, and justice could be differentiated but not separated as these elements are closely related, but they sometimes conflict (antimony). In his Book entitled *Theory of Legislation*, Bentham highlighted the main functions of law as to give norms to utilitarian principle to provide livelihood, to gain a great amount of fortune, encourage equality and maintain safety. With these functions, Bentham struggled to amend murky legislative provisions. Moreover, Bentham remained consistent in maintaining the balance between individual interest and public interest (Atmasasmita, 2012).

John Stuart Mill took further connection between benefits and justice in law. Mill argued that justice standards have to be based on benefits, while the source of justice awareness does not lie in the benefits, but in stimulus to remain in existence and sympathy. The source of justice lies in human conscience to refuse or retaliate over any loss caused. This could be taken by whoever receives sympathy from others. The sense of justice probably stimulates a fight against losses and hardship not only based on individual interest, but it takes a further extent, affecting others seen equal to oneself. Justice principle embraces all moral requirements that are absolute for the welfare of the people (Rahardjo, 1991).

John Stuart Mill related justice to public interest. Unlike John Stuart Mill, Bentham put individual over others. Social institution could be deemed fair as long as it is aimed to optimize benefits for the greatest number of people (people in average) (Vaughan, David G., 2022). However, this notion faced criticism from John Rawls believing that justice was not about optimizing the utilization for all people, but it was rather to provide proportional share for those less fortunate (Vaughan, David G., 2022). However, it is essential to ensure that this controlled partiality does not cause others to suffer and make those less fortunate become parasite.

Thus, John Rawls opined that law as the fundamental element in social structure has to refer to the following two principles:

First, setting equal freedom for each person to gain access to wealth, income, food, protection, wisdom, power, dignity, rights, and freedom; *second*, different principle and the principle of fair equality of opportunity. The different principle represents social and economic differences that have to be adjusted for the greatest benefits to those less fortunate. On the other hand, the principle of fair equality of opportunity represents the opportunity for all people (including those less fortunate) to reach prospects, welfare, income, and authority (Vaughan, David G., 2022).

By managing justice, the development could take place in harmony without any distortion and without jeopardizing the dignity of those less fortunate.

Furthermore, Rudolf von Jhering compared the thoughts expressed by Bentham, Mill, and John Austin following positivism of law. According to Jhering, the objective of law lies in its practical motives, where laws were intentionally made by humans to achieve certain objectives as expected by people (Vaughan, David G., 2022). Due to such a perspective, Jhering is categorized into social utilitarianism that deals with the analysis of law along with its social objectives. Jhering believed that law aims to protect interest and in line with the thought of Jeremy Bentham, Jhering relates interest to happiness hunters (pragmatic) and tendency of avoiding hardship. Jhering also viewed there is a tendency, where individual interest is considered a part of social objectives by comparing personal objectives with the interest of other individuals (Vaughan, David G., 2022). That is, although Jhering agreed with Bentham's notion believing that law is intended to bring the greatest happiness to people and to alleviate hardship, this seems to be the social objectives of law when this is related to individual objectives.

If the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus is compared with the perspective of utilitarian theory, this policy, set forth in Permendikbud Number 3 of 2020, contributes the greatest benefits to the greatest number of university students in terms of the development of hard skills and soft skills. This is also intended to prepare

students with their competence relevant to current development to be the leaders of the state in the future with their excellence and personality that can be optimally achieved.

In Industrial Revolution 4.0, curriculum development seems to be the real challenge in the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus since the curriculum is demanded to shape graduates with high literacy. This policy presents a challenge and opportunity to innovate, to be creative, to have capacity, personality, to meet students' need, and to develop independence in finding and discovering science through the dynamic in real life. The implementation of this program is expected to answer the challenge of higher education required to produce graduates that are capable of adjusting to shifting time, the development of science and technology, pressing demands in industries and businesses, and social dynamic.

Utilitarian theory (utilitarianism) views that law aims to bring the greatest happiness or benefits to people. In analysis, the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus is intended to stimulate students to master science relevant to their knowledge to shape them into more prepared individuals for global world. This policy gives students an opportunity to learn based on their will. The implementation of this policy gives rise to more autonomous and flexible learning process in universities. Education prioritizes benefits for students, shaping them as well educated individuals and agents of change in narrow and wider scopes. These transformation and innovation should give merit and maximum contribution to the development of the state with its quality human resources. This all defines the greatest happiness for the greatest number brought about by utilitarian theory.

4. Conclusions

Departing from the above details, some conclusions can be given:

1. The implementation of the policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus aims to improve the competence of graduates either in terms of their hard skills or soft skills to prepare learners to be excellent and charismatic leaders for the future.
2. Independent Learning Independent Campus has given students their rights to study outside their study programs either in or outside campus. This is relevant to the theory of justice that gives persons rights.
3. Utilitarian theory views that law aims to bring the greatest happiness or benefits to people. The policy of Independent Learning Independent Campus has given great benefits to university students and graduates.

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